

ASPECTS OF CONTACT: RUSSIAN-TURKIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to identify the features of the semantics and functioning of Turkism as part of comparisons in the Russian language. An analysis of the semantics and contextual features of the functioning of Turkism of clothing names was carried out on the basis of the National Corpus of the Russian Language and the Written Corpus of the Tatar Language. The study involved data from explanatory, etymological dictionaries of the Russian language, and dictionaries of stable comparisons.

Russian-Turkic language contacts remain one of the most important tasks of modern linguistics. The study of the reasons, time and ways of penetration of Turkism into the Russian language, their adaptation is one of the problems of the historical lexicology of Slavic languages. In addition, the relevance of the work is related to the aspect of contacting languages of different structures, such as Russian and Turkic languages. Borrowings from Turkic languages form a significant layer of the vocabulary of the Russian language. Unlike Western European borrowings, Turkism mainly relate to everyday vocabulary and therefore for a long time were the only means of naming. Having gone through various stages of adaptation, Turkism mastered by the Russian language are active in the word formation process, they are part of phraseological units, paremiologically units and comparative constructions.

The purpose of the study is to identify the features of the semantics and functioning of Turkism as part of comparisons in the Russian language. An analysis of the semantics and contextual features of the functioning of Turkic clothing names was carried out on the basis of the National Corpus of the Russian Language and the Written Corpus of the Tatar Language. The study involved data from explanatory, etymological dictionaries of the Russian language, and dictionaries of stable comparisons. A high degree of word-formation activity of the units under consideration, acting as a productive basis, has been established. The fact that lexemes enter the active vocabulary is proven by numerous set expressions, proverbs and sayings. One of the most important tasks of modern linguistics is the development of issues of mutual influence of languages, in particular, Russian-Turkic language contacts. According to I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay, "there is not and cannot be a single pure unmixed linguistic whole." Borrowing words from one language to another is a natural consequence of language contacts in all spheres of public life: in the field of politics, economics, science, culture, etc. The history of the

Russian people is closely connected with the destinies of the Turkic-speaking peoples. The result of ethnocultural ties between the Turks and Slavs is a huge number of words borrowed from various Turkic languages (or through Turkic languages). The study of vocabulary of Turkic origin in the Russian language has an established tradition. In the works of scientists, both individual lexico-semantic groups of Turkism and borrowings in written monuments, fiction, dialects of the Russian language, in dictionaries, etc. are analyzed. Turkism, unlike Western European borrowings, are mostly names of household items. In the process of developing figurative meanings, they often expanded their scope of use through various terminological systems. Some Turkism over time acquired a stylistic connotation, often of a negative evaluative nature. Turkism in the Russian language go through all stages of development. Using their example, we can consider various phonetic processes, semantic development of words, and morphological changes. A certain part of Turkism serves as an example of borrowings completely mastered by the Russian language. These lexemes are active in word-formation terms and are the productive basis of word-formation nests; they are phraseological productive and act as a component of stable turns of phrase in the Russian language. An interesting fact that clarifies the etymology of this lexeme is given in the "School Etymological Dictionary of the Russian Language": shoe of Old Russian. borrowed from the Tatars in the language where shoe is "a type of shoe," from shoe "one-year-old calf".

Shoe literally means "shoes made from the skin of a one-year-old calf." In the explanatory dictionary of the Russian language S.I. Ozhegova, the following definitions and translations are given in the N.Yu. Shvedova and Russian-Tatar dictionaries: BASHMAK, -a, m. Boot or low shoe. Explanatory dictionaries provide information about the meaning and word-formation activity of the lexeme: CAFTAN, -a, m. Antique men's long-skirted outerwear.

* Trishkin caftan (colloquial disapproved) – about partial and external corrections that only harm the business and do not bring benefit [according to the fable of the same name by I.A. Krylov]. II decrease-unit. caftanishko, -a, plural. -shki, -shek, -shkam, m. II adj. caftan, -aya, -oe. According to the explanatory dictionary of the Russian language by S.I. Ozhegov, N.Yu. Shvedova: SHAL 1, -i, zh. 1. Large knitted or woven scarf. W. with border. Throw on a sh. on shoulders. Wrap yourself up in sh. 2. Turn-down collar with solid lapels, usually rounded. Shawl collar. II decrease shawl, -i, f. II adj. shawl, -aya, -oe.

The shape, size, color and similar characteristics of a shawl are used as the basis for comparative units in which the objects of comparison are objects, natural phenomena, etc.: The collar should be wide, like a shawl: I will tuck my ears for it (Kozlov) [NKRY]; The second portrait, of Princess Shcherbatova, was painted by Kiprensky in soft and shiny colors, as soft as the silk shawl draped over the princess's shoulders (Paustovsky). The explanatory dictionary gives the following definition and information about derivatives: SHAROVARY, -ar. Wide trousers tucked into the bootlegs; In general, trousers are wide, loose-fitting. Kozatskie highways Tatarskie highways (gathered at the ankles). Sports highways II adj. sharovary, -aya, -oe.

When describing objects (usually different styles of trousers), the basis for comparison can be such characteristics of harem pants as width, length and volume: He was dressed in a light yellow coat, in breeches that were unusual to our eyes, tied around the calves and hanging down like harem pants (Beck) [NKRYA]; Dressed in small felt hats, in trousers as wide as trousers, sewn from small pieces of calico and tied above the ankles with ropes, in a colored vest, they

walked around the bazaars (Shklovsky) Interpretation of the word atlas: ATLAS, -a, m. A type of smooth and shiny silk fabric. II adj. satin, oh, oh. Satin paper (thick and shiny). [Satin skin (translated: soft, delicate). This lexeme is actively used in comparative constructions of the Russian language, acting as a standard of comparison to express similarity in various ways, most often to denote the shine, smoothness of human skin or animal fur: But we also saw several beauties of their kind. What lips, what eyes! The body is as shiny as satin (Goncharov). The study showed that all the Turkisms under consideration are actively involved in the formation of comparative constructions. The lexemes caftan, trousers, shawl are mainly used to describe various objects, and shawl is also often found when describing natural phenomena (sky, forest, sunset) in poetic works. The Turkism shoe is found as part of comparisons when describing a person's appearance, and caftan - when describing processes reminiscent of operations associated with clothing (hanging, putting on, tearing, etc.). The lexeme atlas acts as a standard of comparison most often to denote the smoothness and shine of human skin or animal fur. Thus, the lexemes of Turkic origin that we have considered are completely mastered by the Russian language: they are productive in word formation, act as a component of phraseological units, and actively function in comparative constructions of the Russian language. These lexical units are not perceived in the recipient language as a foreign element; they are able to act as a kind of standard, a measure of ideal quality, action, etc. as part of comparisons when describing objects, natural phenomena, people, etc.

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